

On Beryllium Oxalate

Part. I-Transport, Conductometric and Ion-exchange Studies

A. K. Sengupta and G. Chattopadhyay

Transport experiments with a solution of beryllium oxalate reveals that it remains primarily in the undissociated form. The conductometric titration of beryllium nitrate by potassium oxalatoberyllate show the formation of undissociated beryllium oxalate according to the following equation:

From ion exchange studies of beryllium oxalate and potassium oxalatoberyllate the following equilibria has been found to exist under the conditions of experiments:

Beryllium forms tetrahydrated salts like chloride, sulphate, nitrate etc. having the aquo complex ion $[\text{Be} (\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]^{2+}$. Besides these, beryllium also yields less aquated compounds, such as $\text{Be} (\text{COO})_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Be} (\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ etc.

Beryllium salts are in general weakly conducting, and this property is particularly remarkable in the case of its fluoride, oxalate, malonate, salicylate etc. The low conductivity of all these salts is explained by the low mobility of beryllium ion, which in turn, is attributed to the strong aquation of the beryllium ion.

From E. M. F, conductivity and freezing point measurements of the solutions of beryllium oxalate and malonate Meyer and Mantel,² Sidgwick and others³ have suggested the formation of auto complexes with the following type of dissociation:

where A = oxalate, malonate.

From potentiometric and conductometric measurements of the solutions of beryllium fluoride⁴ and salicylate⁵ the predominant existence of the non-ionic species, $[\text{Be} \text{F}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and $[\text{Be} (\text{C}_7\text{H}_4\text{O}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, have been suggested.

It has also been well known that beryllium salts yield acidic solutions. This

2. J. Meyer and E. Mantel, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1922, **123**, 43.
3. N. V. Sidgwick and N. B. Lewis, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 1287, 2538.
4. R. H. Linnell and H. M. Haendler, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1948, **52**, 819.
5. F. E. Jones *et al*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 563.

has been supposed to be due to the hydrolysis of the aquated beryllium ion by olation and oxolation processes.

In the context of the above facts the present authors found interest in studying the state of highly soluble beryllium oxalate, $\text{Be}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4) \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, in its aqueous solution. For the purpose transport, conductivity and ion exchange experiments have been carried out.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were of reagent quality. Potassium oxalatoberyllate, $\text{K}_2\text{Be}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, was prepared from potassium oxalate and beryllium oxalate according to Rosenheim⁶ and analysed by standard procedures. For the preparation of beryllium oxalate, $\text{BeC}_2\text{O}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, beryllium hydroxide was dissolved by boiling in a solution of oxalic acid (less than stoichiometric amount) and filtered. The solution was analysed for beryllium and oxalate. Then calculated amount of oxalic acid was added and the solution evaporated by heating to yield crystals of the oxalate. The crystals were filtered off by suction, washed with cold alcohol (1:1), then with alcohol and dried in air. The substance was analysed by standard procedures.

The transport experiments were performed according to Duval⁷ utilising an apparatus described by him and taking the necessary precautions. The experiments were carried out using 250 volts (D. C.) line and passing current for four hours. Solutions of beryllium sulphate, beryllium oxalate and potassium oxalatoberyllate were electrolysed using potassium chloride (0.01 M) as the electrolyte for dipping the electrodes in the two stems. After the electrolysis the electrolytes were tested for beryllium by quinalizarine after carrying out necessary chemical operations.

For the conductometric titrations a stock solution of beryllium nitrate was prepared by dissolving beryllium nitrate in water, and standardised by estimating the content of beryllium and nitrate. The solution was analysed and found to contain basic nitrate of beryllium. Therefore, during the preparation of dilute solutions from it requisite amount of nitric acid was added to make the ratio of beryllium and nitrate one to one.

In Fig. 1 the differences of the conductances observed in the titration of beryllium nitrate by potassium oxalatoberyllate, and the sum of the conductances observed in the corresponding blank titrations against water were plotted against the mole ratio $[\text{Be}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]^{2-} \text{Be}^{+2}$. The conductance of the solutions were measured with a Philips conductivity measuring apparatus, Type PR 9500.

The ion exchange experiments were carried out through standard procedures

6. A. Rosenheim and P. Woge, *Z. anorg. chem.*, 1916, **96**, 169,

7. C. Duval *Bull. Soc. Chem. France.*, 1938, 1020.

Figure-1

The difference of the conductances observed in the titration of beryllium nitrate with potassium oxalatoberyllate and the sum of the conductances in the corresponding blank titrations at constant volume.

Curve-I

1 ml (0.3296M) beryllium nitrate titrated with (0.23M) potassium oxalatoberyllate solution at a constant volume of 25 ml.

Curve-II

0.7 ml (0.3296 M) beryllium nitrate solution titrated with (0.0270M) potassium oxalatoberyllate solution at a constant volume of 15 ml.

using columns filled with cation exchanger, Amberlite IR-120 (H^+ form) and anion exchanger Dowex 21 K (C^- form) changed into desired forms by eluting with suitable reagents such as HCl (2 M) and KCl (1 M). In the Table-1 results obtained by starting with solutions prepared by dissolving crystals of beryllium oxalate were tabulated in A and B, whilst the results, which were obtained by using solutions of beryllium oxalate prepared by dissolving beryllium hydroxide into oxalic acid in the one to one ratio, were shown in C,D and E. In F and G the data for the passage of a solution of potassium oxalatoberyllate are given the solution containing known amounts of beryllium and oxalate were passed through resin columns described above and washed with a total volume of 200 ml water. The washings were collected, made to 250 ml in a volumetric flask and analysed for beryllium and oxalate. The resin bed were then eluted with 200 ml of HCl (2 M) or KCl (1 M), the eluate was made to 250 ml by adding water and analysed. Thus ratios of beryllium and oxalate in the various effluents and eluates were determined.

Ion exchange experiments were carried out in a similar manner also using potassium oxalatoberyllate solutions. The results were shown in F and G in Table-1.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The transport experiments with beryllium sulphate and potassium oxalatoberyllate showed the presence of beryllium in the cathode and anode respectively, whilst the experiments with beryllium oxalate showed the absence of beryllium in either of the electrodes. These experiments suggest that in beryllium oxalate solutions, the compound remains mainly in undissociated form.

The conductometric titration of beryllium nitrate by potassium oxalatoberyllate showed a reaction of the two in one to one ratio, which may be written as follows:

The above break thus shows the formation of undissociated beryllium oxalate and the presence of above equilibria predominantly to the right. This observation, therefore, confirms the result obtained above through transport experiment.

The experiments (vide, Table 1) using cation and anion exchangers showed that in the beryllium oxalate solution under the conditions of the experiments in addition to the undissociated oxalate beryllium is present in both the cationic and the anionic species. The average result further showed that in those solutions the amount of beryllium present in the cationic form is in excess to that present in the anionic form. It has also been observed that the dissociation of beryllium oxalate to yield beryllium and oxalate ions becomes almost complete if a cation exchanger in the H^+ form is

TABLE—I

Ion exchange studies with Beryllium Oxalate

Ion Exdchanger (form)	Amounts taken		Effluent		Ratio		Eluant Be mg	Eluate C_2O_4 mg	Ratio	
	Be mg	C_2O_4 mg	Be mg	C_2O_4 mg	Be mg	C_2O_4			Be	C_2O_4
A. Anion-ex changer chloride form	51.6	503.5	32.9	nil	—	—	2MHCl 19.3	492.9	1:2.56	—
B. Cation exchanger potassium form	41.9	416.4	16.2	405.3	1:2.55	—	1MKCl 25.9	nil	—	—
C. Anion exchanger Chloride form	35.0	350.6	20.0	nil	—	—	2MHCl 15.0	343.2	1:2.33	—
D. Cation exchanger potassium form	96.7	902.6	46.2	901.6	1:2	—	2MHCl 48.4	nil	—	—
E. Cation exchanger hydrogen form	83.4	877.9	nil	869.0	—	—	2MHCl 81.3	nil	—	—
F. Cation exchanger hydrogen form	39.5	771.9	nil	770.9	—	—	2MHCl 39.4	nil	—	—
G. Anion exchanger chloride form	20.4	400.0	3.9	nil	—	—	2MHCl 18.0	389.7	1:2.2	—

A to E = The solution passed contains beryllium oxalate

F and G = The solution contains potassium oxalatoberyllate.

utilised (Vide E, Table 1), i.e. the dissociation proceeds to completion at lower pH ranges. This result points to the growing instability of undissociated oxalate in the more acidic ranges.

The results obtained by using potassium oxalatoberyllate solutions (vide F and G, Table 1) indicate that even in these solutions the complex oxalatoberyllate dissociates appreciably to yield beryllium ions (vide infra).

Thus it is clear from the foregoing experiments that in aqueous solution although beryllium oxalate remains predominantly in the non ionic form, the over all equilibrium, can be represented as :

When beryllium oxalate crystals dissolve in water it is but little dissociated according to equation (1) and any reaction which favours the removal of $\text{Be}(\text{OH}_2)_4]^{2+}$ ion from the solution shifts also the equilibrium 1 toward right hand side. The equilibrium (2) is favoured as the acidity increases.

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Department of Chemistry,
Kalyani University,
Kalyani, Nadia.

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